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FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN RUSSIA IN THE POST-SOVIET PERIOD

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Abstract

The article examines the constitutional provisions of 1993 on the fundamentals of the legislation of the Russian Federation on physical culture and sports, on the basis of which laws on physical culture and sports were developed and adopted in most subjects of the Russian Federation. Particular attention is drawn to the fact that, despite significant difficulties, the organizational structure of the management of the industry has been practically preserved in Russia, including – taking into account the specifics of physical culture and sports.

Keywords: sports, history, institute, industry, law.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the problem of introducing a person to physical culture as the main pedagogical task of the development of the physical culture and sports movement in its mass form is indisputable today. The introduction to physical culture of all Russians, especially young people, is declared today as a priority task.

The formation and development of a modern person takes place in complex and contradictory conditions: on the one hand, the scientific and technological revolution contributes to a significant increase in the capabilities of his intellect, and on the other hand, the effect of a number of factors that counteract the full adaptation of a person increases.

In the new historical conditions, within the framework of a new system of social relations, determined, on the one hand, by the laws of the market, and on the other hand, by the values of the culture of the post-industrial society, it is necessary for physical culture to return the role of the most important institution of health, the socialization of the individual, to determine ways to solve the problem of introducing the individual to successful, productive physical culture and sports activities. At the moment, the interest of the state in improving the health of the population, intensifying the mass physical culture and sports movement is noticeable; strengthening the country's position in the international sports arena. The state's position on this issue is reflected in the program "Development of physical culture and sports in the Russian Federation for 2020-2030"; in the "Concept for the modernization of Russian education"; in the National Educational Initiative "Our New School" approved by the President of the Russian Federation; in the Law of the Russian Federation "On Education"; in the Federal Education Standard.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the study is the dialectical principles of the relationship between subject and object, process and result, individual, special and general, the unity of tradition and innovation, methods of analysis, deduction and induction; interdisciplinary approach as the basis of the concept of research, a systematic approach to the study of historical processes; fundamental pedagogical approaches: humanistic, axiological, personality-oriented, activity-based, acmeological, etc.

The scientific and technological essence of organizational and methodological innovations in physical education consists in the priority orientation of the content of the pedagogical process towards introducing students to physical culture, mastering by students the moral, intellectual, behavioral, motor, mobilization, communicative, health-forming and health-saving values of physical culture, including the conversion mechanism acceptable elements of the historical and pedagogical experience of Russia, as well as positive foreign experience in the formation of physical culture in modern physical education in the conditions of the sports environment of the university.

III. RESULTS

The results of the work also give hope for the revival of the mass physical culture and sports movement and the restoration of the continuity of the process of introducing physical culture from the older generation to the younger.

After the collapse of the USSR and the formation of the Russian Federation as an independent state, a new, fundamentally different school program in physical culture was adopted. It is no longer linked to the TRP complex and consists of two parts: mandatory (standard) for all schools and variable (differentiated), developed in specific regions on the principles of local expediency.

Thus, physical education is aimed at strengthening health, the harmonious development of the human body, this is one of the indicators of the state of physical culture in society.

Since 1996, several physical education programs for schoolchildren have been put into effect on the territory of the Russian Federation: a program based on one sport, a comprehensive program, an anti-stress plastic gymnastics program, and author's programs. In fact, this means the termination of the unified program, including its basic part, in all schools of the Russian Federation.

A feature of the programs is that they not only answer the question "what to teach", but also explain "how to teach", i.e. contain a section of methodical recommendations.

Thanks to the development and implementation of such programs, it was possible to maintain the state system of management of physical culture and sports.

Optimization of the management of the "physical culture and sports" industry at the federal and regional levels depends on the creation and improvement of the activity of a specific infrastructure, including such basic elements as an industry information system, specialized financial, credit and legal institutions, etc.

As positive examples, we can mention the creation of the InfoSport industry group, the specialized publishing house Physical Culture, Education, Science, the magazines Physical Culture: Education, Education, Training, Planet Basketball, Theory and Practice of Football, Aerobics. , "Velo: sport, tourism, lifestyle", etc., as well as "SportAka demBank", non-state pension fund "Sport and Health", etc.

Unfortunately, these financial and credit institutions are still working only at the local level. An attempt to create a specialized legal institution "Sports Arbitration", which is extremely necessary for the industry, was unsuccessful for a number of subjective reasons.

One of the specific manifestations of the decentralization of management in the field of "physical culture and sports" is the rather widespread use in recent years of the transfer of various physical culture and sports organizations from federal ownership to the ownership of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation and municipal ownership. Sports schools of various types (DYUSSH, SDYUSHOR, SHVSM), as well as various sports facilities, were most often transferred.

There are also individual examples of the transfer of sports schools of various types from the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Education to the jurisdiction of the state body for managing the industry at the level of a constituent entity of the Russian Federation.

Financing of the branch "physical culture and sports" is carried out from various sources, one of which is the budget.

The Fundamentals of the Legislation of the Russian Federation on Physical Culture and Sports, which were in force from 1993 to 1999, provided for annual financing of the industry from the state budget in the amount of at least 2% of its expenditure. An analysis of the volume of real investment in the industry shows that it did not exceed 0.14% in the specified period (the year of the Olympic Games in Atlanta). This fact is not only evidence of budget financing of the industry according to the so-called residual principle, but also a vivid example of the lack of proper control over the implementation of legislation. The state budget for 2000 (the year of the Olympic Games in Sydney) provided for the allocation of 0.09% of its expenditure for physical culture and sports.

Some "new" sources of financing for physical culture and sports can provide real funds to the budgets of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation and local budgets today. Let's just give one example. Since 1999, all non-state physical culture and sports organizations must obtain a license to carry out their activities. In accordance with the Temporary Licensing Procedure for the Provision of Physical Education and Sports Services, the fee for submitting an application for a license is set at 3 times the minimum monthly wage, and the fee for obtaining a license is 10 times the minimum monthly wage.

The management of the "physical culture and sports" industry in market conditions is increasingly oriented towards targeted programs at both the federal and regional levels.

Describing the federal programs, at least the following facts should be stated. Issues of physical culture and sports are an integral part of the federal programs "Children of Russia", "Youth of Russia", "On social support for the disabled", "On the patriotic education of youth", "On measures to combat crime", "On measures to prevent and prevent distribution of drugs, etc.

Federal sectoral programs of a specific, local nature have been adopted and are being implemented to a certain extent - "Development of tourism in the Russian Federation", "Development of resorts of federal significance", etc. However, the main problem, in our opinion, is that so far not completed and the federal program of a global nature "Development of physical culture and formation of a healthy lifestyle of the population of the Russian Federation", the development of which was started back in the mid-90s of now the last century, has not been adopted.

The situation is more successful in terms of the development of physical culture and mass sports on the basis of targeted programs in the constituent entities of the Russian Federation. To substantiate this conclusion, we will give the following example: in the Orel region in 1996, the Five Year Plan of Health program was adopted and successfully implemented, as a result of two years of implementation of which the level of juvenile delinquency decreased by 26%, serious positive changes were achieved in reducing the incidence rate, and the material and sports base continues to develop.

There is a positive experience in the development and implementation of "private" programs in the field of physical culture and sports in various subjects of the Russian Federation. In Karelia, a package of normative and legal documents has been developed aimed at improving the quality of work of sports schools.

As a result, the number of people involved in them increased by 20%, the number of full-time coaches doubled. In all secondary schools, the rates of teachers-organizers of extracurricular sports activities have been introduced.

In the Samara region, the so-called difficult teenagers are actively involved in sports. Together with the internal affairs bodies, sports organizations involved in sports about 3 thousand children, boys and girls who had "troubles" with the police. After the start of such work, the growth rate of juvenile delinquency decreased by 8 times. There is a similar experience of working with "difficult" teenagers in other regions - in the Oryol, Novosibirsk, Tomsk regions, etc.

One of the pressing problems of modern Russian sports, which required its solution, was the problem of its professionalization. This trend is natural, it is associated with a number of objective conditions for the development of modern sports.

Professionalization of sports, first of all, is the result of its multi-cost, which is dictated by a long educational and training process in many sports, actively continuing for 10-15 years. Early sports specialization is becoming more and more characteristic of big-time sports. In many types, classes begin at the age of 4-6 years. They have been actively going on for many years with two and three workouts a day, accompanied by the highest psychological and physical exertion.

The training of high-class athletes requires expensive logistical support. An actively performing athlete also requires appropriate financial incentives, since he cannot have another source of income due to his huge preoccupation with sports.

Thus, professional sports in the Russian Federation received official legal recognition. For a professional athlete, sports are now recognized as the main activity for which, in accordance with the contract, he receives wages and/or other monetary remuneration, as well as various forms of social and medical insurance. To protect their rights, professional athletes can join professional unions at will.

One of the important directions of improving the legislation of the Russian Federation on sports is a more detailed regulation of the organization, implementation and provision of sports training.

In general, we are talking about creating the foundations of state policy and management practices in the field of physical culture and sports. This is especially important in the modern period, when the system of public administration in Russia depends on the established vertical of power relations and the specification of powers at all levels is becoming increasingly relevant. Physical culture and sports under the Constitution of the Russian Federation are jointly administered by the state authorities of the Russian Federation and the state authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation (Article 72, paragraph "e"). In this regard, it is important to ensure the solution of the following promising areas of development of political and legal foundations in the field of physical culture and sports:

- to clarify the powers of the federal state authorities of the Russian Federation and the state authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation in the field of physical culture and sports; regulation of the organization of effective activities of physical culture and sports communities and organizations engaged in the development of mass physical culture and sports;

- the solution at the legislative level of issues of promotion of physical culture and sports, especially for young people.

A promising direction in the development of legislation on physical culture and sports is the normative development of sports training activities, which is due to the need to eliminate the legal gap expressed in the uncertainty of the status of organizations that train high-class athletes (sports training), including existing schools of higher sports skills, as well as employees of these organizations and athletes undergoing such training.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the optimization of the management system of the "physical culture and sport" industry in market conditions occurs in Russia in two interrelated directions. On the one and, the composition of the elements of the management system is being reorganized at the level of its subjects and objects.

On the other hand, various attempts are being made to improve the very process of functioning of the management system due primarily to the development of a regulatory framework, an increasingly complete transition to program-targeted management, the search for new sources of financial and information support for the development of the industry, etc.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В РОССИИ В ПОСТСОВЕТСКИЙ ПЕРИОД

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Аннотация

В статье исследуются конституционные положения 1993 года об основах законодательства Российской Федерации о физической культуре и спорте, на основе которых разрабатывались и принимались законы о физической культуре и спорте в большинстве субъектов Российской Федерации. Особое внимание обращается на то, что несмотря на значительные трудности, в России практически сохранилась организационная структура управления отраслью, в том числе – с учетом специфики физической культуры и спорта.

Ключевые слова: спорт, история, институт, отрасль, право.

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